

Analysis of Composite Skin/Stringer Bond Failure Using a Strain Energy Release Rate Approach¹

Pierre J. Minguet
Boeing Defense & Space Group
Helicopters Division
Philadelphia PA

T. Kevin O'Brien
U.S. Army Research Laboratory
Vehicle Structures Directorate
NASA Langley Research Center, Hampton, VA

Abstract

A simple test specimen configuration is being used to evaluate the bond strength between a skin and bonded or co-cured frame when the dominant loading in the skin is flexure along the edge of the frame. The specimen consists of a flange bonded onto a skin, loaded in a 4-point bending test fixture. Several skin and flange layups are used to evaluate the influence of the plies near the bondline on the fracture mode. Observations show that failure did initiate at two locations, in the skin or in the flange, near the tip of the flange. Detailed Finite Element models are used to examine the stress distribution in these critical areas. Two analysis methods are considered: the first one, based on the strength of material approach, shows that the formation of a transverse crack is the first step in the failure process. The second method, based on a fracture mechanics approach is then used to determine when a delamination will grow from that transverse crack.

Introduction

With the increased emphasis on reducing the cost of manufacturing composite structures, bonding or co-curing is an attractive option to eliminate the need for mechanically fastening sub-assemblies. Many composite components in aerospace structures consist of flat or curved panels with co-cured or adhesively bonded frames and stiffeners. Out-of-plane loadings such as internal pressure in a composite fuselage or out-of-plane deformations in a compressively loaded post-buckled panel may cause the frame or stiffener to debond from the panel. Previous work [1] conducted for the NASA/Boeing ATCAS program on stiffened panels designed for a pressurized aircraft fuselage has shown that bond failure at the tip of the frame flange is an important and very likely failure mode. That work has also demonstrated that the local moment where the end of the frame or stiffener flange meets the skin is the major contributor to debonding [1]. These tests were conducted with specimens cut from a full-size panel to verify the integrity of the bondline between skin and frame. However, these panels are rather expensive to produce and there is a need for a test configuration that would allow to observe in detail the failure mechanism at the skin/flange interface. A simpler specimen configuration was proposed in Reference 2 to study the failure mechanisms of a bonded skin/flange configuration loaded in bending and transverse shear. The same test specimen configuration is used here to study the influence of the skin and flange layups on the fracture behavior. The information obtained from these tests is used to correlate test data with analytical predictions of the stress field in this critical area and help develop an understanding of the failure mechanisms involved.

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Experimental Investigation

Specimen Configuration

As in Reference 2, the specimen configuration consists of a bonded skin and flange assembly as shown in Figure 1. The goal of this investigation was to examine the influence of the skin and flange stacking sequence on the failure mechanism, and especially the influence of the skin ply angle next to the bondline. Four skin laminates and two flange laminates were selected as shown in Table 1: the skin laminates contained a 0°, 45° or 90° surface ply. Because previous results had shown that the skin bending stiffness has a strong influence on the failure load, all four skin laminates were designed to have nearly the same bending stiffness D_{11} . The two flange laminates were chosen to examine the effect of the relative flange and skin stiffness. Six specimen configurations, labeled A-F in Table 1, were then constructed by combining skin and flange laminates. Both the laminate skin and flange were constructed from IM6/3501-6 graphite/epoxy prepreg tape with a nominal ply thickness of 0.188 mm (0.0074 in). The flange and skin laminates were cured separately at first. The flange parts were then cut in 50 mm (2 in) strips and machined with a 20° taper along the edges. The flange was then adhesively bonded to the skin using a 177°C (350°F) cure film adhesive, American Cyanamid (CYTEC) 1515. A grade 5 film was used, which should result in a nominally 0.127 mm (0.005 in) thick bondline. However, because some of the adhesive flowed outwards during cure, the actual bondline thickness was measured at 0.102 mm (0.004 in). A diamond saw was used to cut the panel into 25 mm (1 in) wide by 127 mm (5 in) long specimens. Figure 1 summarizes the test specimen dimensions.

Table 1. Laminate and Specimen Configurations

Laminate	Layup	D_{11}	Config.	Skin	Flange
S1	[45/-45/0/0/45/90/-45]s	112 N.m (990 in-lb)	A	S1	F1
S2	[0/45/90/-45/45/-45/0]s	117N.m (1034 in-lb)	B	S1	F2
S3	[90/45/0/0/-45/45/-45/90/-45/45/-45/0/0/45/90]	117N.m (1038 in-lb)	C	S2	F1
S4	[45/0/-45/90/45/-45/90/0/90/-45/45/90/-45/0/45]	126 N.m (1111 in-lb)	D	S3	F1
F1	[45/90/-45/0/90]s	22.5 N.m (199 in-lb)	E	S4	F1
F2	[45/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/90]s	108 N.m (954 in-lb)	F	S4	F2

Figure 1. Specimen Dimensions and 4-Point Bending Test Configuration.

Experimental Procedure

A four-point bending test configuration was used in this investigation. Experiments were conducted in a servo-hydraulic load frame using a previously designed and built 4 point bend fixture shown in Figure 1 [Ref. 3]. The bottom support has a 76 mm (3 inch) span, while the upper support has a 102 mm (4 inch) span. The mid-span deflection was monitored using a spring loaded displacement transducer (DCDT) contacting the back side of the skin laminate under the center of the frame flange. Tests for both configurations were performed by controlling the stroke of the upper hydraulic actuator. A plot of the applied load versus the mid-span deflection was recorded on an XY plotter as the test progressed. Three specimens of each kind were tested with the applied stroke increased monotonically until the specimen could not sustain any further load with increasing applied stroke. Two other specimens were then tested incrementally to increasing

load levels, with the specimen removed from the fixture after each load application and the edges examined under a light microscope in the region where the flange terminates.

Test Results

Typical curves of load versus stroke are shown in Figure 2 for two of the specimen configurations. The curves are very linear up to a load level (labeled P_{nl}) at which a very slight deviation from the initial slope is noted as an indication of some possible damage initiation. That initiation was followed by a sudden load drop (P_{vis}) at which the formation of a delamination along one tip of the flange (labeled LHS for "left-hand-side") could be observed visually. In many cases, continued loading produced a second load drop associated with the formation of a visible delamination from the flange on the other side of the specimen (labeled RHS for "right-hand-side"). The formation of these two cracks is then usually followed by a series of load increases and sudden load drops during which delaminations grow in the specimen. For several tests, the load was increased until either a shear failure occurred in the skin between the two rollers on one side of the specimen (configuration B and F) or until slipping of the rollers was observed (configuration A and D).

Figure 2. Typical Load versus Displacement Behavior for Configuration A and D.

Test results are summarized in Table 2. The different loads that are recorded in this Table correspond to the events illustrated in Figure 2. Where available, the load at which a crack formed on the left hand side (P_{vis} LHS) and right hand side (P_{vis} RHS) of the specimen is reported. Note that results for the E configuration are not available at this time.

Table 2 Summary of 4-Point Bending Test Results

Configuration		P_{nl}	P_{vis} LHS	P_{vis} RHS
A	Average	1470 N (331 lb)	1530 N (344 lb)	1615 N (363lb)
	CoV [%]	[4.94]	[4.00]	[6.48]
B	Average	1450 N (326 lb)	n/a	1550 N (349 lb)
	CoV [%]	[4.33]		[8.28]
C	Average	1460 N (328 lb)	1575 N (354 lb)	1735 N (390 lb)
	CoV [%]	[2.83]	[1.61]	[15.8]
D	Average	1220 N (275 lb)	1630 N (367 lb)	n/a
	CoV [%]	[11.0]	[10.6]	
F	Average	1560 N (351 lb)	1645 N (370 lb)	1720 N (386 lb)
	CoV [%]	[4.85]	[4.85]	[4.59]

One of the intents of this test program was to examine the influence of the skin topmost ply angle next to the bondline on failure initiation. Based on previous work, failure always appeared to initiate within that first ply. However, in this investigation, failure initiated in the flange for four out of five configurations, namely A, B, C and F. This is due to the fact that both flange laminates

F1 and F2 include a 90° ply as the second ply away from the bondline. Typical failure patterns for these configurations are shown in Figure 3. Transverse matrix cracks formed in the 90° ply closest to the skin and initiated delaminations at the 90/45 interface. Only in configuration D did failure initiate in the top of the skin. Transverse matrix cracks formed in the 90° ply closest to the flange and either initiated delaminations in the 90/45 interface or created matrix cracks in the 45° ply below which in turn initiated delaminations in the 45/0 interface in the skin. Delaminations once formed tended to stay in the same interface.

Figure 3. Typical Failure Pattern for Configuration D (left) and Configuration A, B, C, F (right).

Analytical Investigation

Finite Element Analysis

The Finite Element Method (FEM) was used to analyze the test specimens. The goal of the analysis was to study damage initiation and propagation, and determine which failure mechanisms are likely to be responsible. Two-dimensional FE models of the specimen cross-section were created for the various configuration specimens. Eight-noded quadrilateral elements are used, and a plane strain condition is assumed. The same material properties used in Ref. 2 are used here.

Figure 4. Overall View of Detailed Finite Element Model and Close-up of Flange Tip Region.

Several model configurations were used in this investigation. The first type, shown in Figure 4 includes a fine element grid in the vicinity of the flange tip. This model was used to study failure initiation and the initial crack propagation. As seen in Figure 4, the model includes a very detailed representation of the tip of the bondline. Four individual plies on either side of the bondline are modeled with three elements used through-the-thickness of each ply. Other plies in that region are modeled with one element through-the-thickness, while “smeared” properties for the skin and flange laminates are used away from this region. This was based on the results of previous models which indicated that interlaminar stresses decayed sufficiently rapidly, both through-the-thickness and away from the flange tip [2]. The other important details that need to be included are the adhesive pocket size, the corner radius of the flange and the thickness of the tip of the tapered flange are all based upon typical dimensions observed in the specimens under the microscope. The tip of the flanges in this study was sharper than that of the specimens used in Reference 2. Thus, the model was modified accordingly and results show that a sharper tip reduces peel stresses in the skin. Symmetric boundary conditions are used at the specimen centerline. Since the load introduction points are far enough from the region of interest,

no details near the load points are included. A total of about 1600 elements and 9700 degrees of freedom are used in the model.

Two forms of analysis were considered to study the onset of failure. The first one is based on a strength of material approach similar to the one presented in Reference 2 where it was proposed that the formation of matrix cracks in plies near the bondline represented the onset of fracture. The maximum tensile principal stress in the transverse (2-3) plane of the unidirectional tape material is used to predict the formation of a transverse crack within a ply:

$$\sigma_{\max} = \frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{2} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33}}{2}\right)^2 + \sigma_{23}^2} \quad \text{where } \sigma_{ij} \text{ are stresses measured in ply axes.}$$

The second form of analysis used here is based on fracture mechanics and a strain energy release rate approach. A transverse crack was introduced in the FE models and a delamination running from the transverse crack was then simulated. In the FE model, crack growth was simulated by releasing nodes along certain ply interfaces and recording the change in potential energy stored in the model. To estimate the relative contribution of Mode I (opening) and Mode II (sliding), the degrees of freedom corresponding to a sliding mode were released first; the change in energy was recorded and designated as the Mode II contribution. The opening degrees of freedom were then released and the change in energy assigned to Mode I.

Figure 5. Location of Matrix Crack and Delamination in Finite Element Models.

The detailed model shown in Figure 4 was used to determine the initial strain energy release rate. Based on the experimental observations and the results shown in the next section, a transverse crack was modeled in the flange 90° ply near the flange tip, with a delamination growing at the 90/45 interface as shown in Figure 5 for configurations “A”, “B”, “C” and “F”. For the “D” configuration, a transverse crack was introduced in the skin 90° ply at the tip of the adhesive fillet, with the delamination running at the 90/45 interface.

Figure 6. Overall View of Simplified Finite Element Model and Close-up of Flange Tip.

A second type of model, shown in Figure 6, does not include as fine an element grid near the tip, but includes more elements along the specimen length. Individual plies and the bondline are represented with one element per ply thickness. This model is used to study crack propagation away from the tip region. A total of about 1000 elements and 6500 degrees of freedom are used in the model.

Stress Analysis Results

Results from the strength of material approach are presented in this section. The first specimen configuration considered is the “B” type. The maximum transverse stress is shown in Figure 7 for three different plies, 90° in the flange, 45° in the flange and 45° in the skin, all three near to the

bondline. Note that in this Figure and in the following ones, the "X" coordinate shown on the horizontal axes runs along the specimen length from the tip of the adhesive fillet and underneath the flange. Stresses are calculated at an applied load level of 1550 N which roughly corresponds to the mean load at which damage became visible in the experiments. The peak transverse stress occurs in the flange 90° ply very near the tip of the flange which is where failure was seen to originate in the experiments. Similar results are shown in Figure 8 for configuration "D" where the maximum stress in the bottom two flange plies and top skin ply are calculated at a load level of 1110 N (250 lb). Unlike for the "B" configuration, the peak stress occurs in the skin 90° ply, which is also where failure was seen to originate in the experiments. The maximum stress in the flange 90° ply for the "A" and "F" configurations are compared with that of the "B" configuration in Figure 9 at an applied load of 1550 N. Results for "A" and "B" are virtually identical, while the peak stress for "F" is slightly lower.

Figure 7. Maximum Transverse Principal Stress for Configuration B.

Figure 8. Maximum Transverse Principal Stress for Configuration D.

If the load at which damage became visible in the experiment is applied to the model, the peak values calculated for the transverse stress are: 57.5 MPa (8345 psi) for "A" at P = 1530 N (344 lb), 58.2 Mpa (8447 psi) for "B" at 1553 N (349 lb) and 58.9 Mpa (8548 psi) for "F" at 1646 N (370 lb). These values are slightly on the high side for the in-situ transverse strength of a 90° ply. If the load P_{nl} was used instead of P_{vis} , the calculated stress would be about 55 Mpa (8000 psi), well within the range of values in which transverse cracks are typically observed to form in 90° plies for laminates under tension loading. If a value of 55 Mpa is used, transverse cracks in the 90° ply would then be expected to appear in the "D" configuration at about 960 N (215 lb). This is well below the load at which a delamination became visible in these specimens. However, results shown in the next section might help explain why the formation of the transverse crack in the "D" specimen does not immediately result in the formation of a delamination.

Another possible failure mode that should be considered is interlaminar tension failure at the interface between two plies. The interlaminar normal stress σ_{zz} is shown in Figure 10 for "B" at an applied load of 1550 N. Two interfaces are considered, the 90/45 in the flange and the +45/-45 in the skin near the bondline. Results show that σ_{zz} is greater in the skin than in the flange. However failure did originate in the flange and the maximum transverse stress appears to be a better predictor of failure initiation, at least for the configurations considered in this investigation.

Figure 9. Maximum Transverse Stress for Configuration A, B and F.

Figure 10. Interlaminar Tensile Stress for Configuration A.

Strain Energy Release Rate Results

Once a transverse crack has formed in a ply, the next question to consider is whether that crack will then initiate a delamination between two plies. To study this problem, a transverse crack was introduced in the FE models and a delamination running from the transverse crack was then simulated with the detailed model shown in Figure 5. The total strain energy release for configuration "B" is shown in Figure 11. Two load levels are shown, $P = 1330 \text{ N}$ and $P = 1550 \text{ N}$, the latter being the average load at which damage became visible. The energy release rate is seen to increase as the crack size increases, which may indicate an unstable growth. The contribution of Mode II is shown in Figure 12, and is fairly constant at about $G_{II}/G_{II} = 3$ as the crack starts to grow. The same results are shown in Figure 13 and Figure 14 for configuration "D". The energy release rate increases even more rapidly than for "B" and the mode ratio varies considerably, becoming more dominantly an opening Mode I as the delamination grows. This is due to the fact that interlaminar normal stress σ_{zz} increases strongly as the delamination moves under the adhesive pocket and the tip of the flange.

Figure 11 Total Strain Energy Release Rate for Configuration B

Figure 12 Contribution of Mode II to Total Energy Release Rate for "B".

In the previous section, it was estimated that a transverse crack would form in the flange 90° ply for the "B" configuration at a load of about 1500 N (340 lb). At that load level, the calculated strain energy release rate for a delamination growing from that crack would be about 170 J/m^2 . For the "D" configuration, the transverse crack in the 90° ply was estimated to form at about 960 N (215 lb). That load level would then produce a calculated strain energy release rate of only 50 J/m^2 . This value is well below that of the "B" configuration and it is therefore not surprising that the formation of a transverse crack in the "D" configuration does not result immediately in a delamination. Data reported in Reference 4 for AS4/3501-6 show that for mixed mode delaminations with Mode II contributing 25% to 35% of the total energy release rate, the critical strain energy release rate ranged from 120 J/m^2 to 155 J/m^2 . Thus for the "B" configuration, the strain energy release rate is very near or above the critical value when a transverse crack forms. For the "D" specimens, damage became visible around 1560 N (350 lb), at which load, the calculated release rate would be 135 J/m^2 , also within the range of critical values reported in Reference 4.

Figure 13 Total Strain Energy Release Rate for Configuration D

Figure 14 Contribution of Mode II to Total Energy Release Rate for "D".

Once a delamination has formed, experiments showed that further load increases were needed to continue crack growth under the flange. To investigate the behavior beyond the initial growth shown in the previous Figures, the strain energy release rate was computed for larger crack sizes using the coarser model shown in Figure 6. Results for the D configuration are shown in Figure 15, and in Figure 16 for the B configuration. The results from the finer model are also shown and can be seen to be consistent with the results from the coarser model. These calculations show that the strain energy release rate increases rapidly and then levels off to a constant value as the delamination progresses beyond the tapered flange tip. However, that value is about three or four times higher than the critical value necessary to initiate crack propagation. Since experiments did not show an unstable growth across the whole length of the specimen, this could mean that the critical strain energy release rate increases once the delamination grows to a finite size. Also, if the critical release rate did not increase, it would then be impossible to reach a load high enough to create failure on the opposite side of the specimen. However, further work is needed to quantify the growth of a delamination past its initial stage. Also shown in Figure 15 and Figure 16 are the strain energy release rates calculated by prolonging the transverse crack through the next ply and growing a delamination at a different interface than that used for the initial propagation, in both cases one ply lower in the skin or flange. Results show that the release rate increases there and it is therefore not surprising that delaminations were observed to jump to these interfaces.

Figure 15. Total Strain Energy Release Rate for Configuration D.

Figure 16. Total Strain Energy Release Rate for Configuration B.

Conclusion

The use of a strength of material approach based on the maximum transverse tensile stress in plies adjacent to the bondline appears to correctly predict the location of the onset of failure. Furthermore, the value of the transverse stress calculated at an applied load equal to the peak load measured experimentally is consistent with the ply in-situ transverse strength. Once a transverse crack has formed, a strain energy release rate analysis can be used to determine when a delamination will grow from the matrix crack.

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